

Microfluidic fabrication of vesicles with hybrid lipid/nanoparticle bilayer membranes

Julie Perrotton,^{ab} Rubén Ahijado-Guzmán,^a Lara H. Moleiro,^a
Berta Tinao,^a Andrés Guerrero-Martinez,^a Esther Amstad,^b
Francisco Monroy^{*a,c} and Laura R. Arriaga^{†*a}

^a Department of Physical Chemistry, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, 28040, Madrid, Spain.

E-mail: lrarriaga@quim.ucm.es

^b Institute of Material Science, Ecole Polytechnique Federale de Lausanne (EPFL),
CH-1015, Lausanne, Switzerland

^c Translational Biophysics - Imas12, IIS Hospital Doce de Octubre, 28041 Madrid, Spain

† Current address: Departamento de Ingenieria Quimica Industrial y Medio Ambiente,
Escuela Tecnica Superior de Ingenieros Industriales,
Universidad Politecnica de Madrid, 28006, Madrid, Spain.

Received 8th October 2018, Accepted 21st December 2018

DOI: 10.1039/c8sm02050g

Abstract

Hybrid lipid/nanoparticle membranes are suitable model systems both to study the complex interactions between nanoparticles and biological membranes, and to demonstrate technological concepts in cellular sensing and drug delivery. Unfortunately, embedding nanoparticles into the bilayer membrane of lipid vesicles is challenging due to the poor control over the vesicle fabrication process of conventional methodologies and the fragility of the modified lipid bilayer assembly. Here, the utility of water-in-oil-in-water double emulsion drops with ultrathin oil shells as templates to form vesicles with hybrid lipid/nanoparticle membranes is reported. Moreover, upon bilayer formation, which occurs through dewetting of the oil solvent from the double emulsion drops, a phase separation is observed in the vesicle membrane, with solid-like nanoparticle-rich microdomains segregated into a continuous fluid-like nanoparticle-poor phase. This phase coexistence evidences the complex nature of the interactions between nanoparticles and lipid membranes. In this context, this microfluidic-assisted fabrication strategy may play a crucial role in thoroughly understanding such interactions given the uniform membrane properties of the resulting productions. Furthermore, the high encapsulation efficiency of both the vesicle membrane and core endows these vesicles with great potential for sensing applications and drug delivery.

Introduction

The incorporation of nanoparticles (NPs) into the hydrophobic core of the membrane of lipid vesicles is of utmost importance for many technological applications including biomedical imaging and sensing.¹ Since lipid membranes are extremely thin, only NPs with sizes of the order of the membrane thickness can be stably embedded inside the hydrophobic core of the lipid bilayer assembly.² Larger particles cause oversized membrane deformations, leading to membrane destabilization and rupture.³ Moreover, since the intrabilayer core of a lipid membrane is hydrophobic, the NPs must possess a hydrophobic or amphiphilic surface to ensure their successful embedding.⁴ NPs fulfilling these two requirements can be potentially incorporated into the membrane of lipid vesicles; however, the lateral distribution of NPs within lipid membranes is highly dependent on the fabrication method.⁵ Hydration of hybrid lipid/NP lamellar phases results in the formation of lipid vesicles with a homogeneous distribution of NPs in their membrane.^{5,6} By contrast, mixing of NPs and preformed lipid vesicles results in the preferential incorporation of NPs into a hemispherical membrane domain;⁵ this may be due to the energy cost associated to membrane deformation, which can be reduced if NPs are incorporated into previously nucleated membrane domains that are already deformed by the presence of other NPs. Furthermore, in both fabrication methods, vesicles with NP-loaded membranes coexist with vesicles with bare membranes;⁵ this evidences the poor degree of control over NP concentration provided by conventional vesicle fabrication methods, which is a major drawback and significantly limits the applicability of these hybrid lipid/NP vesicles. Vesicles with hybrid NP/polymer membranes can be fabricated with exquisite control over their size, encapsulation efficiency and concentration of NPs within the polymer membrane using double emulsion drops with relatively thick shells as templates.⁷ However, such templates are not suitable for the fabrication of vesicles with hybrid lipid/NP membranes; this is likely due to both the lower stability of double emulsion drops with thicker shells relative to those with thinner shells, and the higher fragility associated to lipid membranes, as they are generally thinner than polymer membranes. Therefore, strategies to fabricate lipid vesicles with hybrid lipid/NP membranes, controlling the concentration of NPs within the vesicle membrane remain a great challenge; the controlled fabrication of these vesicles will greatly enhance the potential of hybrid lipid/NP vesicles as sensors.⁸

Here, we report the utility of water-in-oil-in-water (W/O/W) double emulsion drops with ultrathin oil shells as templates for the production of vesicles with hybrid lipid/NP membranes. This approach, originally developed for the fabrication of lipid vesicles⁹ and later used for the fabrication of polymer-based membranes,¹⁰ is here adapted to the challenging case of hybrid lipid/NP membranes, achieving an excellent performance. In this adaptation, the ultrathin oil shell of the double emulsions consists of a mixture of hydrophobic NPs and phospholipid molecules suspended in a mixture of chloroform and hexane. This mixture of solvents is designed to form hybrid lipid/NP membranes through a dewetting transition, similar to that observed during the formation

of polymersomes,¹¹ which facilitates solvent removal. The resulting vesicles are monodisperse in size, because of the size monodispersity of the double emulsion drops used as templates, and able to efficiently encapsulate fluorescently labelled molecules, owing to the high encapsulation efficiency of microfluidic technologies. Interestingly, the resultant hybrid lipid/NP membranes exhibit laterally segregated NP-rich domains with irregular boundaries, which resemble gel-fluid membrane coexistence domains.¹² Furthermore, upon budding,¹³ these vesicles exhibit flat boundaries in certain membrane regions, which also evidences the gel-like character of NP-rich domains. Such clustering of NPs into NP-rich domains can be understood on the basis of a reduction of the total membrane deformation.¹⁴ The excellent control over the membrane composition achieved by this microfluidic approach may enable the fine engineering of hybrid lipid/NP membranes.

Experimental

Chemicals

1-Palmitoyl-2-oleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocoline (POPC) is purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids Inc. Dextran from *Leuconostoc* spp. (70 kDa), and poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA, 13-23 kDa, 87-89% hydrolyzed), along with the organic solvents, chloroform and hexane, are all purchased from Sigma. 1,2-Dihexadecanoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine- N -(lissamine rhodamine B sulfonyl) (DHPE-Rh), purchased from Molecular Probes, is used to label the vesicle membrane and fluorescein isothiocyanate-dextran (FITC-dextran, 20 kDa), purchased from Sigma, is used to label the vesicle cores. Milli-Q water from a Millipore system (resistivity $18.2\text{M}\Omega\text{cm}^{-1}$) is used to prepare the aqueous phases, to synthesize the nanoparticles, and as subphase for the isotherms.

Nanoparticle synthesis

A solution of AuCl_4^- (5mM, $500\mu\text{L}$) and a freshly prepared solution of BH_4^- (1M, $100\mu\text{L}$) are added under vigorous stirring to 50 mL of Milli-Q water. The solution turns orange immediately after mixing. After 1 min, the solution turns deep red. After 5 more minutes, the release of hydrogen bubbles is observed. The nanoparticle suspension is then mixed with 10 mL of hexane containing $100\mu\text{L}$ of dodecanthiol. The suspension is shaken vigorously for 1 min. This process enables the transference of the nanoparticles to the organic phase, which is then isolated by liquid-liquid extraction.¹⁵

Fabrication and operation of the glass-capillary device

Square-molded borosilicate glass capillaries with internal size of 1.05 mm are purchased from Atlantic International Technology. Cylindrical, single-barrel standard borosilicate glass capillaries with an external diameter of 1.00 mm and internal diameter of 0.58 mm are purchased from World Precision Instruments. The round capillaries are tapered to a diameter tip of $20\mu\text{ m}$ using a micropipette puller (P-2000, Sutter Instrument, Inc.). Sand paper (2500 grit) is then used to widen the tip diameters of the round capillaries to 90 and $150\mu\text{ m}$, for the injection and collection capillaries, respectively. The injection capillary is treated with trimethoxy(octadecyl) silane (Sigma) to make it hydrophobic, whereas the collection capillary is treated with 2-[methoxy(poly-ethyleneoxy)9-12propyl] trimethoxysilane (Gelest) to render its surface hydrophilic. The tips of these two capillaries are immersed in their respective silane treatment for about 15 min, followed by drying using compressed air. An additional round capillary is then stretched using a burner to a typical external diameter of about $100\text{--}200\mu\text{ m}$ and inserted into the injection capillary without further treatment. To build the device, the square capillary is first fixed onto a microscope slide with 5 min curable epoxy resin (Devcon). After surface treatment, the two round capillaries are inserted in the opposite ends of the square capillary, and their axis are aligned on the microscope, leaving a separation distance between them of about $80\mu\text{ m}$. These capillaries are then fixed to the slide with the same epoxy resin. Next, the stretched capillary is inserted inside the injection capillary and also fixed to the slide. Finally, dispensing needles with luer-lock connections (0.5'' needle length, 20 gauge) are placed at the junctions between capillaries or their ends, and fixed to the slide. The 5 min epoxy resin is left to completely cure for 24 hours before injecting any liquids into the device.

Three pumps (PHD 2000 Infusion, Harvard Apparatus), an inverted microscope (Nikon Eclipse TE2000-E, with a $10\times$ dry objective), and a high-speed camera (Phantom V7) are used to conveniently operate this glass capillary device. The two aqueous phases are filtered through $5\mu\text{ m}$ filters (Acrodisc) before injection in the microfluidic device, after which they are injected in the device using 5 mL Becton plastic syringes. The oil phase is injected using a 5 mL Hamilton gastight syringe, due to the incompatibility of the organic solvents with plastic syringes. Each syringe is placed on a pump and connected to one of the device inlets with polyethylene tubing of inner diameter of 0.86 mm (Scientific Commodities, Inc.); this allows injection of each phase at the adequate flow rate to form the water-in-oil-in-water double emulsion drops with ultrathin shells.

Imaging

The formation of double emulsion drops in the microfluidic device is recorded using a $10\times$ dry objective on an inverted microscope (Nikon Eclipse TE2000-E)

equipped with a highspeed camera (Phantom V7). The formation of the vesicles from the double emulsion drops is monitored using bright-field (Nikon Eclipse TE2000-E) and confocal fluorescence microscopy (Nikon C⁺). Two-channel fluorescence images are simultaneously acquired using a 20 \times dry objective on this confocal microscope. For this, two different lasers are used as excitation sources: 488 nm for FITC-dextran and 561 nm for DHPE-Rh; the fluorescence emission is collected by the PMT detectors through band-pass filters between 524 and 550 nm for the FITC-dextran channel, and between 570 and 1000 nm for the DHPE-Rh channel. For the monolayers, we use the same confocal fluorescent microscope as for the vesicles with a 5 \times dry objective. For the transmission electron microscopy (TEM) characterization of the NPs, a drop of the NP colloidal suspension is dried on a 200 mesh carboncoated copper grid and then observed under a JEOL JEM 2100 operating at 200 kV . Image J is used to estimate the size of the NPs from transmission electron microscopy images, and the size of the double emulsion drops from optical microscope images.

Surface pressure-area isotherms

A computer-controlled Langmuir balance (medium size, NIMA, UK) is used to measure the surface pressure, Π , versus area, A , isotherms of POPC in the presence and absence of NPs. This setup consists of a Teflon trough with a maximum area of 273 cm² (NIMA, UK), equipped with two symmetrically moving barriers made of hydrophilic Delrin, and a surface pressure sensor (PS4). To measure the surface pressure we use a paper Wilhelmy plate (Whatman CHR1 chromatography paper, effective perimeter 21 mm , supplied by NIMA), ensuring a constant contact angle. In these experiments, the paper is placed perpendicular to the barriers. To form the pure POPC monolayer, POPC dissolved in chloroform at a concentration of 1mgmL⁻¹ is spread on the surface of the water subphase using a Hamilton syringe. To form the hybrid POPC/NP monolayer, POPC dissolved in chloroform at 1mgmL⁻¹ is mixed with the hexane suspension of NPs, resulting in a suspension containing 0.36mgmL⁻¹ of POPC and the same concentration of NPs as in the vesicles, 2.4 mg mL ; this suspension is spread on the water subphase. After spreading, the monolayers are left to equilibrate for 30 min . Then, the compression isotherms are measured upon compression of the monolayers at a constant velocity of 10 cm² min⁻¹. The isotherms are plotted against the mean molecular area, A , obtained dividing the total surface area of the trough by the amount of POPC spread on the water surface; the amount of NPs is not considered in this representation. Isotherms are measured at 25°C. The dilational elasticity modulus is obtained as $\varepsilon_0 = -A(\partial\Pi/\partial A)$, performing the numerical derivative on an interpolation of the isotherm that contains 35 pairs of data points.

Interfacial shear rheology

The same solutions used to measure the isotherms are used to prepare monolayers on top of a water subphase contained in the Delrin trough of an interfacial rheometer system (TA Instruments, Discovery, HR2). We then use the Double Wall Ring (DWR) geometry to determine the elasticity of the monolayers upon oscillation of the tool at an angular frequency of 1 rad s^{-1} and deformation of 1%.

Results and discussion

Double emulsion drops with thin shells

We use a co-flow glass capillary microfluidic device to fabricate double emulsion drops with ultrathin shells.¹⁶ The device consists of two cylindrical capillaries facing each other and aligned inside a square capillary, as illustrated schematically in the top panel of Fig. 1(A). Inside the injection capillary, on the left, the device contains an additional smaller capillary that is used to inject the innermost aqueous phase. This phase consists of an aqueous solution of 8 – 9wt% dextran (70 kDa) and 2 – 1wt% poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA, 13-23 kDa); the dextran increases the density of the double emulsions, which thus sink upon collection, while PVA increases the stability of the double emulsions, enabling their successful transformation into vesicles. This polymer solution also contains fluorescently labelled dextran, fluorescein isothiocyanatedextran (FITC-dextran, 20 kDa), which enables us to visualize the double emulsion or the vesicle cores by confocal fluorescence microscopy. The middle oil phase, a mixture of 5 mg mL^{-1} of 1-palmitoyl-2-oleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocoline (POPC) and 2.4 mg mL^{-1} of dodecanthiol-functionalized gold nanoparticles suspended in a mixture of 36vol% chloroform and 64vol% hexane, is injected into the injection capillary. These nanoparticles with a typical diameter of approximately 4 nm , and variation coefficient of 20%, as determined from image analysis of transmission electron microscope (TEM) images, are shown in the TEM image of Fig. 1(B). This middle phase also contains a small amount of a fluorescently labeled phospholipid, 1,2-dihexadecanoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphoetanolamine- *N*-(lissamine rhodamine B sulfonyl) (DHPE-Rh), which enables us to visualize the double emulsion shell and the vesicle membrane. Both inner and middle phases co-flow at a typical flow rate of $500 \mu \text{ L h}^{-1}$, forming a train of water drops surrounded and spaced by oil, as illustrated in Fig. 1(A). The outermost water phase, a 10wt% PVA solution, is injected through the interstices between the injection and square capillaries, at a typical flow rate of $3000 \mu \text{ L h}^{-1}$; this process re-emulsifies the water drops, generating W/O/W double emulsion drops with ultrathin shells, as shown in the bottom image of Fig. 1(A). Under these flow rate conditions, the device operates in the so-called discontinuous dripping regime, in which the production of double emulsion drops alternates with the production of single emulsion drops.¹⁶ Both types of drops are easily sepa-

rated upon collection due to their different densities; the double emulsion drops containing polymer molecules in their core sink, whereas single emulsion drops float, thereby remaining at the top of the collection vial. A typical production of double emulsion drops collected in an initially empty vial is shown in the optical microscopy image of Fig. 1(C); these have an average diameter of $96\mu\text{m}$ and a typical coefficient of variation of 4%, as determined from image analysis.

Hybrid lipid/NP vesicles

We use these double emulsion drops as templates to form vesicles with hybrid phospholipid/NP membranes. Importantly, the oil shell of these emulsion drops is very thin, of the order of a micrometer; this feature increases the stability of the double emulsion drops and enables the formation of phospholipid vesicles through dewetting of the middle phase solvent.⁹ To achieve dewetting,¹¹ the middle oil phase is designed as a mixture of a highly volatile good solvent, chloroform, and a less volatile bad solvent for phospholipids, hexane, at a typical volume ratio below but close to the cloud point of the phospholipids. The chloroform starts to evaporate as soon as the double emulsion drops leave the production device and continues to diffuse to the aqueous phase once the drops are in the collection vial. Diffusion of chloroform from the middle phase drastically reduces the solvent quality, forcing the phospholipids in the middle phase to precipitate; this ultimately leads to an attraction between the two phospholipid monolayers adsorbed at the O/W interfaces of the double emulsion drops, triggering a solvent dewetting phenomenon. A complete dewetting transition is not observed, as evidenced by the presence of solvent in the time sequence of images shown in Fig. 2(A); the remaining hexane forms an oil pocket, as pointed by the white arrow in the last frame of Fig. 2(A), which continues to evaporate over the course of several days. Moreover, the precipitated excess lipid material accumulates in this oil pocket, as shown by the increased fluorescence intensity of that region in the confocal fluorescence images of Fig. 2(B), also indicated by a white arrow in Fig. 2(C). Because dewetting is incomplete the final concentration of lipids and NPs in the resultant vesicular structure is the same one that we inject in the device (5mgmL^{-1} POPC and 2.4mgmL^{-1} NPs). The formation of the pocket could be potentially avoided replacing the mixture of chloroform and hexane by 1-octanol, an approach successful for the production of fluid-like lipid vesicles;¹⁷ however, the hydrophobic character of the NPs used in this study prevents the use of 1-octanol as middle phase solvent in this case.

The hybrid phospholipid/NP membranes formed through such a dewetting transition exhibit microdomains, observed as dark regions in the confocal fluorescence images of Fig. 2(B) and (C). The observed phase separation is likely a membrane deformation related phenomenon. Given that our NPs are stably suspended in hexane, the inter-particle potential does not change from repulsive to attractive during chloroform evaporation. Moreover, after chloroform evaporation, double emulsion droplets do not exhibit phase separation; phase separation is observed solely after hexane dewetting. Moreover, it has been shown that the

presence of NPs in the bilayer induces membrane deformations. In particular, the membrane region where a particle is located bends to accommodate the spherical particle shape; this involves bending of the outer and inner membrane monolayers in opposite directions, thereby causing "unzipping" of the bilayer.⁵ When several particles are present in the bilayer, the total membrane curvature can be reduced by lateral aggregation of the NPs, which reduces the total free energy of the system.⁵

We hypothesize that the dark regions observed in Fig. 2 are nanoparticle-rich, gel-like microdomains, which coexist with a continuous nanoparticle-poor, fluid-like phase that is fluorescently labelled by DHPE-Rh due to its disordered nature. To test this hypothesis, we perform a thermodynamic study of the pure POPC and the hybrid POPC/NP systems using a Langmuir balance, as structural transitions are typically easy to identify in the surface pressure isotherms of their monolayers.¹⁸ As expected, the surface pressure isotherm of POPC displays a monotonous liquid expanded (LE) or fluid-like shape with a collapse pressure of about 50 mN m^{-1} , as shown by the discontinuous line in Fig. 3(A). By contrast, the surface pressure isotherm of a monolayer of POPC containing the same concentration of NPs as in the vesicles displays a phase transition quasi-plateau starting at a typical surface pressure of approximately 33 mN m^{-1} , as shown by the continuous line in Fig. 3(A). The surface pressure value of this quasi-plateau is very close to the surface pressure value corresponding to the bilayer packing.¹⁹ Then, we observe the texture of the different monolayers at this pressure state using the confocal microscope. The hybrid POPC/NP monolayer exhibits dark domains, similar to those observed in the vesicles, whereas the texture of the bright POPC monolayer is uniform, as shown in the top fluorescence confocal images of the inset to Fig. 3(A). Such dark domains exhibit irregular shapes, much like in the hybrid POPC/NP vesicles, shown in Fig. 2(B) and (C). Moreover, these dark domains differ significantly to the dark domains formed during the transition between the gas (G) and liquid expanded (LE) phases of the same monolayer, which are circular, as shown in the bottom fluorescence confocal image of the inset to Fig. 3(A). We therefore conclude that these dark domains correspond to a liquid condensed (LC) or gel-like phase that coexists with the continuous LE or fluid-like phase.

To get further insight about the distribution of NPs into the observed coexisting phases, we study the mechanical properties of the POPC/NP system. First, we determine the quasi-equilibrium values of the dilational elasticity modulus, ε_0 , as the numerical derivative of the surface pressure isotherms. The pressure dependence of the dilational elasticity is very different for POPC and hybrid POPC/NP monolayers, as shown in Fig. 3(B). For the POPC monolayer, ε_0 increases with surface pressure up to a maximum value of approximately 130 mN m^{-1} , and then drops to zero immediately before the monolayer collapses. For the hybrid POPC/NP monolayer, the value remains essentially constant, at a value of approximately 30 mN m^{-1} , upon increasing surface pressure up to the quasi-plateau. This ε_0 value is significantly lower than that of the POPC monolayer, which indicates that the LE phase of the hybrid monolayer is significantly

softer or more disordered than that of the LE phase of POPC. This indicates the possible presence of at least a small quantity of NPs within the continuous LE phase of the vesicle, likely acting as defects that prevent POPC packing upon compression. Further compression makes ε_0 to drop to a value of approximately 12mNm^{-1} at the surface pressure value corresponding to the bilayer packing; this ε_0 value is significantly larger than zero. For a first-order phase transition at infinitely low compression speed, one should find a perfectly horizontal plateau in the surface pressure-area isotherms and thus ε_0 should drop to a value of strictly zero. This is the case of isotherms of a single type lipid monolayer, such as those of 1,2-dipalmitoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DPPC), obtained at zero-compression speed, using the so-called addition strategy.²⁰ However, even in this single type lipid monolayer case, the slope of the theoretically horizontal plateau increases with compression speed, which results in finite values of ε_0 ; this can be due to either the finite growth rate of phase coexistence domains,²⁰ or the presence of impurities.²¹ Given that our hybrid monolayer consists of a mixture of lipids and NPs, the observed phase transition might not be first-order. Furthermore, because the isotherms are performed at the standard finite compression rate of $10\text{ cm}^2\text{ min}^{-1}$, plateau horizontality could be limited by the speed of growth of the NP-rich domains, which results in a value of ε_0 larger than zero at the plateau. For surface pressure values above the plateau, ε_0 remains at a maximum value of approximately 30mNm^{-1} . This LC phase is thus softer than the LE phase of POPC at this surface pressure, indicating that POPC molecules are unable to pack tightly in the presence of NPs. Therefore, we can conclude that the two phases coexisting in the vesicles have similar values of the dilational elasticity, owing to the presence of NPs. Complementarily, we measure the shear elasticity modulus, G' , for the same hybrid POPC/NP monolayer at the collapse pressure, obtaining a value of $10\mu\text{ N m}^{-1}$, measured for a deformation of 1% at an angular frequency of 1rads^{-1} , using a stress-controlled interfacial rheometer. By contrast, G' for POPC is strictly zero, as expected for a fluid.²² Therefore, given that the hybrid system supports shear, we can conclude that the LC phase of the vesicles is a solid and thus, it is likely to be enriched in nanoparticles, as pure POPC layers are fluid; this also justifies the irregular boundaries of the LC microdomains.

The fact that the fluorescently labelled phospholipid, DHPERh, is excluded from the microdomains also confirms that microdomains are more condensed than the continuous fluorescent phase. DHPE-Rh, the dye used in our study has shown a total segregation from gel domains of 1,2-dimyristoyl-sn-glycero-3phosphoethanolamine (DMPE).²³ In that work, it is discussed that given that DHPE-Rh possesses a very large polar headgroup because of the presence of the rhodamine moiety, the very stable arrangement of the DMPE gel phase prevents the insertion of this fluorescent probe. For the same reason, our stable arrangement of NP-rich phase should prevent dye insertion as well. Moreover, we selected this lipid dye, having two saturated hydrocarbon chains in addition to the large fluorescent moiety, to ensure its depletion from NP-rich membrane regions based on the difficulty of saturated phospholipids to bend to accommodate NP-induced membrane deformations. Furthermore, the shape of phase

coexistence microdomains is strongly correlated to the difference in composition between the resultant fluid and gel phases. Domains with dendritic shapes, as those shown in Fig. 2, have been observed before in binary phospholipid mixtures made of either a mixture of 1,2-dilauroyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DLPC) and 1,2-diarachidoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DAPC) or a mixture of DPPC and 1,2-dipalmitoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine (DPPE).²³ The dendritic domains appear dark when labelled with the same dye as we are using, and exhibit very low intensity when using Laurdan as a probe. Importantly, Laurdan measurements allowed correlating dendritic shapes to large compositional differences between coexistence phases.²³ Therefore, in the abovementioned systems, dark dendritic domains represented an almost pure gel, whereas the bright continuous phase represented an almost pure fluid phase. Analogously to these binary systems, dark dendritic domains in our hybrid POPC/NP membrane represent the gel phase and thus the NP-rich phase, whose composition we expect to be very different to that of the fluid phase given the resultant dendritic shapes, as smaller compositional differences frequently result in line or quasi-circular shapes. These considerations justify the preferential partition of DHPE-Rh in the more expanded phase and its exclusion from the more tightly packed microdomains. However, we cannot completely exclude that the dye may suffer quenching in the nanoparticle-rich regions due to resonant energy transfer with the gold nanoparticles in these regions.²⁴

Despite chloroform is a better solvent than hexane for phospholipids, excess phospholipids, those that are not needed to form a bilayer with optimum packing, are dewetted in the hexane phase together with the fluorescent probes.⁹ The dewetted drop attached to the vesicles is more fluorescent than the bilayer in both absence and presence of NPs;⁹ thus, the fluorescence of the hexane drop does not provide any information on the nanoparticle concentration in the dewetted drop.

Importantly, in the vesicles, we do not observe mutual coalescence of NP-rich microdomains. This is in stark contrast with the typical behavior observed for liquid-like domains, which typically form by the phase separation of a ternary mixture of lipids containing a saturated phospholipid, an unsaturated phospholipid and cholesterol into a liquid disordered and a liquid ordered phase. These liquid-like domains are circular, very dynamic and frequently coalesce into two different hemispherical regions, thereby resulting in the ultimate formation of Janus-like vesicles.^{9,25} We therefore conclude that the concentration of NPs in these dark regions is larger than that in the continuous fluid phase, although we cannot exclude the possible presence of some NPs in the continuous phase regions. Importantly, the uniformity in the presence of microdomains in every vesicle of a typical production, which is exemplified by Fig. 2(B), evidences the excellent control achieved by this microfluidic approach over the concentration of NPs incorporated in the lipid membrane, in stark contrast with former approaches in which vesicles with and without NPs in their membranes coexist in the same batch.

In-vesicle encapsulation and compartmentalization

Another major advantage of this microfluidic approach is its excellent encapsulation efficiency compared to that of conventional vesicle preparation methods. In this microfluidic approach, the inner water phase remains completely separated from the outer water phase during the whole vesicle fabrication process, leading to encapsulation efficiencies of practically 100%. This means that every vesicle in the production encapsulates the same concentration of molecules, as shown by the uniform fluorescence intensity of the inner cores of the double emulsions of Fig. 4(A), which is that of the inner water phase. This efficient encapsulation is maintained during the dewetting transition; thus, the model encapsulant, FITC-dextran, remains efficiently encapsulated within the lumen of the resultant vesicles, as shown by the green color in Fig. 4(B). The orange color in Fig. 4(B) arises from the overlay of the two fluorescence channels; the dark membrane regions are greenish in the overlaid image, whereas the bright membrane regions appear orange due to the superposition of the green and red channels. By contrast, encapsulation efficiencies of conventional fabrication methods are of the order of 35%.²⁶

Further evidence of the solid-like character of the dark NP-rich membrane domains is obtained upon vesicle budding. To induce vesicle budding, we increase the osmolarity of the outer water phase allowing the water to evaporate up to a osmotic pressure difference of approximately 50mOsmkg^{-1} ; this induces a water outflow from the inner cores of the vesicles towards the outer water phase, thereby concentrating the encapsulated polymers, which are dextran and PVA. At high enough concentrations, these two polymers, which differ significantly both chemically and in their molecular weights, phase separate,²⁷ as shown in the bright-field and confocal fluorescence images in Fig. 5(A) and (B), respectively. The dextran-rich domain appears darker in the bright field image of Fig. 5(A) and green in the confocal fluorescence image of Fig. 5(B), whereas the PVA-rich domain appears brighter in the bright-field image and as green dye-exclusion zones in the confocal fluorescence image. The white arrows in Fig. 5(A and B) indicate the PVA-rich compartments within the cores of the double emulsions. If the concentration of polymers in the lumen of the resultant vesicles increases further, the interfacial tension between these two polymer phases increases as well and thus the two phases try to minimize their contact area; this ultimately results in membrane budding as shown in the optical microscopy image of Fig. 5(C).²⁸ Upon budding, the larger membrane region is the darkest one, as shown in Fig. 5(D), indicating that the solidlike NP-rich domains tend to occupy the less curved membrane region. By contrast, the fluid continuous phase, which appears red in the confocal fluorescence image of Fig. 5(D), accommodates in the region of larger curvature, since a fluid membrane region is easier to bend than a solid one. Moreover, the solid character of certain regions is further evidenced by the existence of flat edges in the otherwise spherical larger caps; one of these flat regions is highlighted by the straight white line in Fig. 5(D), which is intended as a visual guide. Although the fluid membrane regions are concentrated in the smaller caps, there are also

fluid regions separating solid domains in the larger caps, as evidenced in the confocal fluorescence images shown in Fig. 5(E) and (F).

Conclusions

The use of double emulsion drops with ultrathin shells, fabricated using microfluidic technologies, as templates for vesicles provides a versatile strategy to fabricate hybrid lipid/NP vesicles with uniform sizes and carefully controlled concentrations of NPs in their membrane. Dewetting of the middle phase solvent from the double emulsion drops results in the formation of a phospholipid bilayer that encapsulates the hydrophobic gold NPs in its core. The hydrophobic interactions established between the surface of the NPs and the hydrophobic chains of the phospholipids ensure the stability of lipid/NP nanoassembly. Phase separation into NP-rich and NP-poor microdomains is observed upon bilayer formation. NP clustering into NP-rich domains can be understood on the basis of the energy penalty associated with the ruffling deformation of the membrane by a single NP; the total membrane deformation is smaller for a NP cluster than for the same number of NPs that form the cluster deforming the membrane individually. The exquisite control over membrane composition achieved with our microfluidic approach enables the fine engineering of vesicles comprising hybrid lipid/NP membranes, making these membrane systems attractive models for the investigation of the complex interactions between nanoparticles and ubiquitous lipid membranes. Moreover, this approach may be useful as well to fabricate vesicles for sensing applications after careful assessment of their biocompatibility. Furthermore, this fabrication concept opens up the possibility of performing hydrophobicity-driven chemistry in the intrabilayer space of lipid vesicles fabricated using microfluidic-assisted templating strategies.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by a Marie Curie International Outgoing Fellowship within the EU Seventh Framework Programme for Research and Technological Development (GUVs-3G, PIOF-2012332078), the Spanish Ministry of Economy MINECO by both a Juan de la Cierva - Incorporacion Fellowship (IJCI-2014-22461) and a Plan Nacional grant in the Retos Program (FIS2015-70339-C2-1-R), and the Comunidad de Madrid (S2013/MIT-2807).

Notes and references

- 1 (a) W. T. Al-Jamal and K. Kostarelos, *Nanomedicine*, 2002, 2, 85; (b) Y. Chen, A. Bose and G. D. Bothun, *ACS Nano*, 2010, 4, 3215.
- 2 (a) H. S. Wi, K. Lee and H. K. Pak, *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter*, 2008, 20, 494211; (b) M. Schulz, A. Olubummo and W. H. Binder, *Soft Matter*, 2012, 8, 4849; (c) D. Boicchio, E. Panizon, L. Monticelli and G. Rossi, *Sci. Rep.*, 2017, 7, 6357.
- 3 M. R. Rasch, Y. Yu, C. Bosoy, B. W. Goodfellow and B. A. Korgel, *Langmuir*, 2012, 28, 12971.
- 4 (a) G. D. Bothun, *J. Nanobiotechnol.*, 2008, 6, 13; (b) W. H. Binder, R. Sachsenhofer, D. Farnik and D. Blaas, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2007, 9, 6453; (c) H. Zhang, Q. Ji, C. Huang, S. Zhang, B. Yuan, K. Yang and Y. Ma, *Sci. Rep.*, 2015, 5, 10525.
- 5 M. R. Rasch, E. Rossinyol, J. L. Hueso, B. W. Goodfellow, J. Arbiol and B. A. Korgel, *Nano Lett.*, 2010, 10, 3733.
- 6 G. Gopalakrishnan, C. Danelon, P. Izewska, M. Prummer, P.-Y. Bolinger, I. Geissbuhler, D. Demurtas, J. Dubochet and H. Vogel, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2006, 118, 5604.
- 7 E. Amstad, S.-H. Kim and D. A. Weitz, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2012, 51, 1.
- 8 J. Song, J. Zhou and H. Duan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2012, 134, 13458.
- 9 L. R. Arriaga, S. S. Datta, S.-H. Kim, E. Amstad, T. E. Kodger, F. Monroy and D. A. Weitz, *Small*, 2014, 5, 950.
- 10 D. F. do Nascimento, L. R. Arriaga, M. Eggersdorfer, R. Ziblat, M. F. V. Marques, F. Reynaud, S. A. Koehler and D. A. Weitz, *Langmuir*, 2016, 32, 5350.
- 11 (a) R. C. Hayward, A. S. Utada, N. Dan and D. A. Weitz, *Langmuir*, 2006, 22, 4457; (b) H.-C. Shum, J.-W. Kim and D. A. Weitz, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2008, 130, 9543; (c) H.-C. Shum, E. Santanach-Carreras, J.-W. Kim, A. Ehrlicher, J. Bibette and D. A. Weitz, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, 133, 4420.
- 12 (a) E. J. Schimshick and H. M. McConnell, *Biochemistry*, 1973, 12, 2351; (b) K. Jorgensen and O. G. Mouritsen, *Biophys. J.*, 1995, 95, 942; (c) L. A. Bagatolli and E. Gratton, *Biophys. J.*, 2000, 78, 290.
- 13 J. Kas and E. Sackmann, *Biophys. J.*, 1991, 60, 825.
- 14 (a) H. Aranda-Espinoza, A. Berman, N. Dan, P. Pincus and S. Safran, *Biophys. J.*, 1996, 71, 648; (b) U. Schmidt, G. Guigas and M. Weiss, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2008, 101, 128104.
- 15 M. N. Martin, J. I. Basham, P. Chando and S.-K. Eah, *Langmuir*, 2010, 26, 7410.
- 16 S.-H. Kim, J. W. Kim, J.-C. Cho and D. A. Weitz, *Lab Chip*, 2011, 11, 3162.
- 17 S. Deshpande, Y. Caspi, A. E. C. Meijering and C. Dekker, *Nat. Com.*, 2016, 7, 10447.
- 18 (a) H. Mohwald, *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 1990, 41, 441; (b) C. M. Knobler, *Adv. Chem. Phys.*, 1990, 77, 397; (c) H. M. McConnell, *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, 42, 171; (d) C. M. Knobler and R. C. Desai, *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 1992, 43, 207.
- 19 D. Marsh, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta, Biomembr.*, 1996, 1286, 183.

- 20 L. R. Arriaga, I. Lopez-Montero, J. Iñes-Mullol and F. Monroy, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2010, 114, 4509.
- 21 N. R. Pallas and B. A. Pethica, *Langmuir*, 1985, 1, 509.
- 22 G. Espinosa, I. Lopez-Montero, F. Monroy and D. Langevin, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.*, 2011, 108, 6008.
- 23 L. A. Bagatolli and E. Gratton, *Biophys. J.*, 2000, 79, 437.
- 24 E. Dulkeith, A. C. Morteani, T. Niedereichholz, T. A. Klar, J. Feldman, S. Levi, F. C. J. M. van Veggel, D. Reinhoudt, M. Moller and D. I. Gittins, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2001, 89, 201002.
- 25 T. Baumgart, S. T. Hess and W. W. Webb, *Nature*, 2003, 425, 821.
- 26 H.-C. Shum, D. Lee, I. Yoon, T. Kodger and D. A. Weitz, *Langmuir*, 2008, 24, 7651.
- 27 C. R. Mace, O. Akbulut, A. A. Kumar, N. D. Shapiro, R. Derda, M. R. Patton and G. M. Whitesides, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2012, 134, 9094.
- 28 (a) Y. Liu, R. Lipowsky and R. Dimova, *Langmuir*, 2012, 28, 3831; (b) M. S. Long, A.-S. Cans and C. D. Keating, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2008, 130, 756; (c) Y. Li, R. Lipowsky and R. Dimova, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2008, 130, 12252; (d) M. Andes-Koback and C. D. Keating, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, 133, 9545.

Fig. 1 (A) Schematic illustration of the microfluidic device used to produce double emulsion drops with ultrathin shells (top) and bright-field microscopy image showing a production at typical flow rates of the inner, middle and outer phases of $500, 500$ and $3000 \mu\text{L h}^{-1}$, respectively (bottom). (B) Transmission electron microscopy image of dodecanthiol-functionalized gold nanoparticles. (C) Bright-field microscopy image showing the obtained double emulsion drops collected in an initially empty vial.

Fig. 2 (A) Time sequence of images showing the oil dewetting from a double emulsion drop and further solvent evaporation. Time lapse between images is approximately 10 min . (B and C) Confocal fluorescence images of the resultant vesicles. The membrane is labeled with DHPE-Rh. The white arrows indicate the initial solvent pocket, where excess lipids are accumulated as evidenced by the enhanced fluorescence intensity in that region.

Fig. 3 (A) Surface pressure-area isotherms of pure POPC and hybrid POPC/NP Langmuir monolayers. Inset: Confocal fluorescence microscope images of POPC and POPC/NP Langmuir monolayers at surface pressures of approximately 33 mNm^{-1} (top) and 1 mNm^{-1} (bottom). (B) Variation of the dilational elasticity modulus as a function of surface pressure for pure POPC and hybrid POPC/NP Langmuir monolayers.

Fig. 4 Overlaid confocal fluorescence images showing the (A) double emulsion drops and (B) vesicles. The red color is due to the fluorescence of DHPE-Rh, the phospholipid used to label the shell of the emulsions and the membrane of the vesicles, whereas the green color corresponds to the fluorescence of FITC-dextran, the fluorescently labeled dextran encapsulated in the inner cores of the double emulsions and vesicles.

Fig. 5 (A) Bright-field microscopy image showing the formation of compartments within the water cores of the double emulsions formed by the phase separation of an aqueous mixture of dextran and PVA. (B) Overlaid confocal fluorescence image showing the preferential partition of FITC-dextran in the dextran-rich compartments of the double emulsions. The white arrows in panels (A) and (B) indicate the PVA-rich compartments. (C) Bright-field microscope image showing vesicle budding upon further concentrating the polymers in the vesicles. (D) Overlaid confocal fluorescence image showing the partition of FITC-dextran, in green, in the dextran-rich compartment of the vesicle, which is preferentially surrounded by a NP-rich membrane region, as evidenced by the absence of fluorescence in the membrane region of smaller curvature. The straight white line is a visual guide to the flat edge of the vesicle. (E and F) Overlaid confocal fluorescence images showing in red the preferential accommodation of the fluid phase membrane in the regions of higher curvature.